

SANDWICH BEAMS WITH MID-PLANE ASYMMETRY SUBJECTED TO LATERAL LOADS – ANALYSIS AND OPTIMIZATION

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SUMMARY: The equations with which to analyze, design and optimize sandwich beams, which involve mid-plane asymmetry, are presented. Both classical beam theory and a refined theory involving transverse shear deformation are discussed. Explicit solutions for the beam subjected to a uniform lateral load for the boundary conditions of both ends clamped; both ends simply supported and a cantilevered beam are given. To obtain minimum weight, the means to select each face thickness and the core depth are given for a given material system. In order to choose the face materials to achieve a minimum weight beam, a factor of merit is defined. Various materials are then compared.

KEYWORDS: sandwich beams, minimum weight optimization, mid-plane asymmetry.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich construction offers many advantages over conventional monocoque construction particularly when the loads result in bending of the structure. The use of composite materials in the faces of sandwich structures provides another means to reduce weight while incorporating many of the other advantages of composites such as damping, corrosion resistance and very high strength to weight and stiffness to weight ratios. Traditionally sandwich construction has employed faces of the same material and thickness such that the sandwich is mid-plane symmetric regardless of the many materials used for the face.

However mid-plane asymmetry could offer many advantages such as having the outer face be thicker than the inner face to better resist impact, thermal or wear loads while the inner face could be made more resistant to chemical attack, toxicity or fire, for example. Thus mid-plane asymmetry, which inevitably results in bending-stretching coupling, can be used to effectively produce a superior sandwich structure.

In the present research the simplest of structures, the beam is used to investigate the effects of using mid-plane asymmetry in sandwich construction. Several boundary conditions are studied, i.e. clamped-clamped, simple-simple and cantilever, for the beam subjected to uniform lateral load.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Consider a beam of length L , width b , face thicknesses, t_{f1} and t_{f3} , and core depth h_c as shown in Fig. 1. Assuming that there is a lateral distributed load per unit area $p(x)$ acting, and that there are no surface shear stresses, the following equilibrium equations hold, where N_x , M_x and Q_x are the in-plane stress resultant per unit width, the stress couple per unit width and the transverse shear resultant per unit width, respectively. x is the coordinate in the length direction.

$$\frac{dN_x}{dx} = 0 \quad \frac{dQ_x}{dx} = p(x) \quad \frac{dM_x}{dx} = Q_x \quad (1)$$

Since in a beam there is no variation in the y direction, i.e. the width direction, it is traditional and easy to multiply the quantities by the beam width b , and to define the usual beam quantities of in-plane force (P), transverse shear resultant (V), and bending moment or stress couple (M_b) and the load per unit length (q).

$$P \equiv N_x b, \quad V \equiv Q_x b \quad M_b \equiv M_x b \quad q(x) \equiv p(x)b \quad (2)$$

Taking into account the usual classical beam assumptions, the constitutive equations for a mid-plane asymmetric beam are [1]

$$N_x = A_{11} \mathbf{e}_x^0 + B_{11} \mathbf{k}_x \quad M_x = B_{11} \mathbf{e}_x^0 + D_{11} \mathbf{k}_x \quad (3)$$

where, for the classical beam case

$$\mathbf{e}_x^0 = \frac{du_0}{dx} \quad \mathbf{k}_x = -\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \quad (4)$$

In (3) above the stiffness matrix quantities are written in the usual form for $i, j = 1, 2, 6$ [1] as

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N (\overline{Q}_{ij})(h_k - h_{k-1}) \quad B_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^N (\overline{Q}_{ij})(h_k^2 - h_{k-1}^2) \quad (5)$$

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^N (\overline{Q}_{ij})(h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3)$$

In many sandwich constructions involving foam, solid or honeycomb cores, the core contribution to the extensional stiffness A_{ij} and the flexural stiffness D_{ij} is negligible.

Further, for many of these constructions the face thicknesses (t_{f1} and t_{f3}) are very small compared to the core depth, (h_c) i.e. t_{f1} and $t_{f3} \ll h_c$.

In that case for the beam in Fig. 1:

$$A_{11} = E_{f1}t_{f1} + E_{f3}t_{f3} \quad B_{11} = \frac{h_c}{2} (E_{f3}t_{f3} - E_{f1}t_{f1}) \quad (6)$$

$$D_{11} = \frac{h_c^2}{4} (E_{f1}t_{f1} + E_{f3}t_{f3}) = \frac{h_c^2}{4} A_{11}$$

The mid-plane asymmetry parameter \mathbf{f} was defined by Vinson [2], as:

$$\mathbf{f} = \frac{B_{11}}{\sqrt{A_{11}D_{11}}} \quad (7)$$

For the asymmetric sandwich beam, using (6), \mathbf{f} becomes:

$$\mathbf{f} = \left[\frac{-1 + \frac{E_{x3}t_{f3}}{E_{x1}t_{f1}}}{1 + \frac{E_{x3}t_{f3}}{E_{x1}t_{f1}}} \right] = \frac{E_{x3}t_{f3} - E_{x1}t_{f1}}{E_{x3}t_{f3} + E_{x1}t_{f1}} \quad (8)$$

It is seen that in all cases $-1 \leq \mathbf{f} \leq 1$, where $\mathbf{f} \rightarrow -1$ as the lower face stiffness dominates, and $\mathbf{f} \rightarrow +1$ when the upper face stiffness dominates.

Substituting (4) and (7) into (3) the governing equations (1) are obtained as:

$$\frac{d^2 u_0}{dx^2} = \frac{B_{11}}{A_{11}} \frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} \quad V_b = -b(1 - \mathbf{f}^2) D_{11} \frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} \quad (9), (10)$$

$$\frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} = \frac{q(x)}{b(1 - \mathbf{f}^2) D_{11}} \quad (11)$$

BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The various possible boundary conditions for the mid-plane asymmetric beam [3] are,

Simple Support:	Clamped:	Free:
$w = 0$	$w = 0$	$M_b = 0$
$M_b = 0$	$\frac{dw}{dx} = 0$	$V_b = 0$
$P = 0$	$u_0 = 0$	$P = 0$

(12)

Using the above boundary conditions the governing equations can be solved. It may be pointed out here that rigid body motion is avoided by specifying $u_0 = 0$ at some location.

BEAM SOLUTIONS

Solving for the simple case of a clamped-clamped beam with a uniformly distributed lateral load - q_0 , one obtains:

$$u_0(x) = \frac{B_{11}}{A_{11}} \frac{q_0}{24b(1-f^2)D_{11}} (6Lx^2 - 4x^3 - 2L^2x) \quad (13)$$

$$w(x) = -\frac{q_0}{24b(1-f^2)D_{11}} (x^4 - 2Lx^3 + L^2x^2) \quad (14)$$

$$w_{\max} = w(L/2) = -\frac{q_0L^4}{384b(1-f^2)D_{11}} \quad (15)$$

To calculate the stresses at the upper and lower faces, the stresses for any laminate are found by [1],

$$(\mathbf{s}_x)_k = [\bar{Q}]_k (\mathbf{e}_{x_0} + z\mathbf{k}_x) \quad (16)$$

It must be remembered that due to the bending-stretching coupling induced by the B_{11} term, $\mathbf{e}_{x_0} \neq 0$ in the beam. For the sandwich, the lower face coordinates are $-\frac{h_c}{2} - t_f \leq z \leq -\frac{h_c}{2}$, while the upper face coordinates are $\frac{h_c}{2} \leq z \leq \frac{h_c}{2} + t_f$. In the case of $t_f/h_c \ll 1$ the face coordinates may be approximated as $z = \pm h_c/2$. Hence the maximum stresses which occur at $x=0$ and $x=L$ at the ends of the beam are:

$$\mathbf{s}_{f1\max} = -\frac{q_0L^2}{12bt_{f1}h_c} \quad \mathbf{s}_{f3\max} = \frac{q_0L^2}{12bt_{f3}h_c} \quad (17)$$

It can be seen that the maximum stress in the lower face is negative, while the maximum stress in the upper face is positive. This is to be expected since in a clamped-clamped beam the lower face is in compression and the upper face in tension at each end, with the load being - q_0 .

Substituting expressions for f and D_{11} , and expressing t_{f1} and t_{f3} in terms of $\mathbf{s}_{f1\max}$ and $\mathbf{s}_{f3\max}$ above, one obtains the following expression for the maximum deflection.

$$w_{\max} = \frac{L^2}{h_c} \frac{1}{32} \left(\frac{\mathbf{s}_{f1\max}}{E_{x1}} - \frac{\mathbf{s}_{f3\max}}{E_{x3}} \right) \quad (18)$$

For this case $\mathbf{s}_{f1\max}$ is in compression, hence a negative value, see (17), therefore the bracketed quantity is additive providing the negative deflection. It is seen that for this case, (17) and (18) provide the equations which for the analysis of an already designed beam one can determine if the

maximum stresses and maximum deflections are less than or equal to the allowable values. In design, one can determine the face thicknesses t_{f1} and t_{f3} and the core

depth h_c to insure that the allowable values of tensile face stress, compressive face stress and maximum deflection are not exceeded.

Using similar techniques the maximum values of face stresses and deflection for the simple-simple and cantilever beams subjected to the same uniform lateral load per unit length, $-q_0$ can also be obtained.

For the simple-simple case

$$w_{\max} = w(L/2) = -\frac{5}{384} \frac{q_0 L^4}{b(1-f^2)D_{11}} \quad (19)$$

$$\mathbf{s}_{f1\max} = \frac{q_0 L^2}{8bt_{f1}h_c} \quad \mathbf{s}_{f3\max} = -\frac{q_0 L^2}{8bt_{f3}h_c} \quad (20), (21)$$

From the stress equations it is evident that in the simple-simple case too, the stress equations are consistent, giving tensile stress in the lower face and compressive stress in the upper face. Following similar steps as in obtaining equation (18), the equivalent expression for the simple-simple case is:

$$w_{\max} = -\frac{L^2}{h_c} \frac{5}{48} \left(\frac{\mathbf{s}_{f1\max}}{E_{x1}} - \frac{\mathbf{s}_{f3\max}}{E_{x3}} \right) \quad (22)$$

And for the cantilever case,

$$w_{\max} = w(L/2) = -\frac{q_0 L^4}{8b(1-f^2)D_{11}} \quad (23)$$

$$\mathbf{s}_{f1\max} = -\frac{q_0 L^2}{2bt_{f1}h_c} \quad \mathbf{s}_{f3\max} = \frac{q_0 L^2}{2bt_{f3}h_c} \quad (24), (25)$$

$$w_{\max} = \frac{L^2}{h_c} \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\mathbf{s}_{f1\max}}{E_{x1}} - \frac{\mathbf{s}_{f3\max}}{E_{x3}} \right) \quad (26)$$

MINIMUM WEIGHT OPTIMIZATION

In all of the above as well as the solution for any lateral load, any set of boundary conditions, and any combination of materials for the faces, one always arrives at the equations, such as (15), (17), (18), (19)-(22) and (23)-(26). These involve maximum stresses, which for each face can go to the allowable compressive stress \mathbf{s}_{Call} , which is a negative number, and the allowable tensile stress \mathbf{s}_{Tall} , which is a positive number. The allowable stresses are defined as the ultimate compressive or tensile stress divided by a factor of safety. They also involve the maximum allowable lateral deflection, w_{all} which is a negative number if the load is in the negative direction. Also with these

three allowable stress and deflection values, there are also three dependent variables, t_{f1}, t_{f3} , and h_c , by which the structure can be made minimum weight, for a given set of face and core materials.

The beam weight per unit plan form area W , less the corresponding weight of the adhesive bond material, W_{ad} , which is non analytical, can be written as:

$$W - W_{ad} = \mathbf{r}_{f1}t_{f1} + \mathbf{r}_{f3}t_{f3} + \mathbf{r}_c h_c \quad (27)$$

If for example, one substitute the values of t_{f1} and t_{f3} for the clamped-clamped beam subjected to the uniform lateral load - q_0 , described in (17) above, one obtains:

$$W - W_{ad} = -\frac{\mathbf{r}_{f1}q_0L^2}{12bh_c\mathbf{s}_{Call}} + \frac{\mathbf{r}_{f3}q_0L^2}{12bh_c\mathbf{s}_{Tall}} + \mathbf{r}_c h_c \quad (28)$$

Substituting for h_c in (28) above using (18) one finally can obtain

$$W - W_{ad} = \frac{8q_0w_{all}}{3b} \left(\frac{-\frac{\mathbf{r}_{f1}}{\mathbf{s}_{Call}} + \frac{\mathbf{r}_{f3}}{\mathbf{s}_{Tall}}}{\left(\frac{\mathbf{s}_{Call}}{E_{x1}} - \frac{\mathbf{s}_{Tall}}{E_{x3}} \right)} \right) + \frac{\mathbf{r}_c L^2}{32w_{all}} \left(\frac{\mathbf{s}_{Call}}{E_{x1}} - \frac{\mathbf{s}_{Tall}}{E_{x3}} \right) \quad (29)$$

In this equation it is seen that on the right hand side the first term represents the weight per unit planform area of the two faces while the second term represents the weight of the core. Keep in mind that \mathbf{s}_{Call} is negative, and in this case w_{all} is negative also because the lateral load is negative.

The loading and the maximum deflection are specified quantities. It is also obvious that for whatever the loading and whatever the maximum deflection of the beam, the materials, which makes the first, term at minimum are the best (optimum) materials. Thus a factor of merit (F.M.) for materials selection can be defined as follows

$$F.M. = \frac{\left(\frac{\mathbf{s}_{Tall}}{E_T} - \frac{\mathbf{s}_{Call}}{E_C} \right)}{\left(\frac{\mathbf{r}_{fT}}{\mathbf{s}_{Tall}} - \frac{\mathbf{r}_{fC}}{\mathbf{s}_{Call}} \right)} \quad (30)$$

Wherein the subscripts T represents the face where the maximum tensile stress occurs and subscript C represents the face in which maximum compressive stress occurs. Note that this factor of merit for materials selections is the same for each of the three problems treated explicitly herein. In fact it is the same factor of merit for any other lateral set of loads and for any other boundary conditions as well. Now using (30) one can select the materials, which will result in the minimum weight beam structure

for any lateral load and any boundary condition. In the case where $E_T = E_C$ and $\mathbf{s}_{Tall} = -\mathbf{s}_{Call}$, then

$$F.M. = \frac{\mathbf{s}_{all}^2}{E\mathbf{r}_f} \quad (31)$$

Obviously for a beam, only the material properties in the length direction are used in any of the equations above. Notice also that in (29), the core weight is not affected by the magnitude of the lateral load, only by w_{max} and the face properties.

BEAMS INCLUDING THE EFFECTS OF TRANSVERSE SHEAR DEFORMATION

If transverse shear deformation effects are included the curvature \mathbf{k}_x is given by

$$\mathbf{k}_x = \frac{d\bar{\mathbf{a}}}{dx} \quad (32)$$

for this case the transverse shear resultant expression in (1) is written as

$$Q_x = A_{55} \left(\bar{\mathbf{a}} + \frac{dw}{dx} \right) \quad (33)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{a}}$ is the rotation of a lineal element through the beam thickness. N_x and M_x have usual meanings. Substituting (32) in (3) one obtains the governing equations.

$$\frac{d^2 u_0}{dx^2} = -\frac{B_{11}}{A_{11}} \frac{d^2 \bar{\mathbf{a}}}{dx^2} \quad (34)$$

$$V_b = (1 - \mathbf{f}^2) b D_{11} \frac{d^2 \bar{\mathbf{a}}}{dx^2} = b A_{55} \left(\bar{\mathbf{a}} + \frac{dw}{dx} \right) \quad (35)$$

$$\frac{dV_b}{dx} = -q_0 \quad (36)$$

where $A_{55} = G_c h_c$, G_c being the shear modulus of the core material or the effective shear modulus of the honeycomb core. Substituting the first relation for (35) into (36) if one solves for $\bar{\mathbf{a}}$, then using the second relation one can solve for lateral deflection w , which for a simply supported beam using the boundary conditions in (12) is obtained as,

$$w(x) = \frac{q_0}{bA_{55}} \left[\frac{x^2}{2} - \frac{Lx}{2} \right] - \frac{q_0}{24bD_{11}(1-\mathbf{f}^2)} \left[x^4 - 2Lx^3 + L^3x \right] \quad (37)$$

$$w_{\max} = w\left(\frac{L}{2}\right) = -\frac{q_0 L^2}{8bA_{55}} - \frac{5}{384} \frac{q_0 L^4}{bD_{11}(1-f^2)} \quad (38)$$

Note that the second term in (38) is identical to the classical beam theory result of (19). To obtain face stresses one utilizes (16) where now $k_x = d\bar{a}/dx$. Following through it is found that for this case of the beam simply supported at each end, the face stresses are identical to the values given by classical theory, i.e. (20) and (21). However when transverse shear deformation effects are included, the modified maximum displacement equation, in this case (38) must be used to determine the required core depth h_c . In this example problem from (38) it is seen that the ratio of the maximum deflection including transverse shear effects to that of classical beam theory is:

$$\frac{(w_{\max})_{tsd}}{(w_{\max})_{classical}} = 1 + \frac{48}{5} \frac{D_{11}(1-f^2)}{A_{55}L^2} \quad (39)$$

Similar expressions will result from other beam solutions wherein only the numerical coefficient varies for each solution.

SAMPLE CALCULATIONS FOR OPTIMIZED SANDWICH BEAM

For the materials listed in Table 1., the Factors of Merit, (30) are given in Table 2., where the common factor of safety of unity was used.

Table 1. *Material Properties*

	Material	s_T GPa	E_T GPa	s_c GPa	E_c GPa	r kg/m^3	Reference
1	Unidirectional AS/3501 Graphite Epoxy	1.447	138	1.447	138	1900	[1]
2	Unidirectional Kevlar49/Epoxy	1.400	76	0.235	76	1500	[1]
3	Unidirectional Eglass/epoxy	1.2894	60.7	0.8205	60.7	2540	[1]
4	7178-T6 Aluminum	0.5385	71.8	.5385	71.8	2829.3	[4]

Table 2. *Factor of Merit*

Tension-Compression	Factor of Merit 10^3	Tension-Compression	Factor of Merit 10^3
1-1	7.99	1-3	5.44
2-2	2.89	2-1	12.1
3-3	6.86	2-3	7.66
4-4	1.43	3-1	9.66
1-2	1.76	3-2	2.91

Thus among the materials the Kevlar/epoxy tension face and the Graphite/epoxy compression face is best (F.M. 12.1). The next highest is Eglass/epoxy for the tension face and a graphite/epoxy compression face (F.M. 9.66), but a beam optimized for this material system could weigh 25.3 % more (i.e. $12.1/9.66=1.253$) than the optimum Kevlar-graphite faced system discussed above. Also the optimum 7178-T6 Aluminum would weigh 8.46 times the optimized Kevlar-graphite fiber system above.

CONCLUSIONS

From the above, methods have been derived to analyze the mid-plane asymmetric sandwich beam subjected to lateral loads for various boundary conditions. For the analysis of a structure these methods can be employed to determine the face stresses and deflections for a given set of loads, boundary conditions for the material systems being considered. For design one can determine the face thicknesses and core depth to insure that the structure is not overstressed or overdeflected. For minimum weight optimization of the beam structure, for given loads and boundary conditions, and for each set of materials considered, unique values of each face thickness and core depth are found in terms of the tensile and compressive allowable stresses and moduli of elasticity of each face material. The employment of the unique values of the face thicknesses and the core depth results in the minimum weight construction using those materials. Then comparing the weight of each material system using the Factor of Merit defined herein provides the selection of the best materials to achieve minimum weight.

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Fig. 1 *Cross-Section of a Mid-Plane Asymmetric Sandwich*